

Role of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) System Protocols in Infertility Treatment: A Case Study of A 29-Year-Old House Wife with History of Recurrent Spontaneous Miscarriages and Ovarian Cysts

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Recurrent spontaneous miscarriage (RSM) affects 1 to 2 % of women causing anxiety and worry for self and family. Ovarian cysts are perhaps the most common issue among women trying to conceive. This paper presents a case of a 29-year-old married woman having ovarian cyst and suffered two miscarriages, was treated successfully using YPV healing protocols.

METHOD: This paper used case study method going through patient medical records, healer's records and patient feedback.

RESULTS: The patient experienced successful pregnancy and delivered a healthy baby boy after a C-section procedure. There were no health issues of baby and the mother post-delivery. A follow up after 9 months confirmed that the mother and her baby both were in good health.

CONCLUSIONS: YPV system protocols have been established as complementary as well as alternative medicine to treat and cure a variety of health conditions. Further research is recommended. It will be worthwhile to consider imparting a working knowledge of YPV system protocols to frontline healthcare workers including doctors and nurses to enable them to render holistic treatment in a safe process at low cost.

KEYWORDS: Recurrent Spontaneous Miscarriage (RSM), ovarian cyst, infertility, Yoga Prana Vidya System ®, YPV®

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INTRODUCTION

A case of a 29-year-old woman patient who suffered RSM (Recurrent, Spontaneous Miscarriage) two times had been referred to a Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healer based in Pune, Maharashtra, India for a review and design of an appropriate YPV intervention and execute it to achieve success at attempting pregnancy 3rd time desiring a healthy baby.

On examination of the case, it had been revealed that the patient had a history of:

1. A first-time miscarriage, happened when a baby was not formed (May 2019)

2. A second-time miscarriage, happened due to preterm labour during 2nd trimester (24 Nov 2020)

3. Diagnosed with a right ovarian haemorrhagic cyst (45 x 21 mm)

4. Anxiety and worry anticipating further failures

The patient approached the healer through a referral seeking YPV healings along with medications as she had earlier tried to sustain her conception twice but encountered failures. This paper presents this case study of successful treatment using YPV system protocols leading to normal pregnancy and healthy child birth.

METHOD

This paper has used case study method going through patient medical records, YPV intervention records and patient feedback.

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YPV INTERVENTION

Healing Treatment for Ovarian Cysts:

When the case was referred to the healer, the patient was observed to be suffering from emotional imbalance (negative thoughts, anxiety) due to two successive RSM, and a condition diagnosed to be right ovarian cysts.

A USG test taken on 11 January 2021 showed right ovarian cyst of size 45X21 mm.

The healer consulted the patient with empathy to know all about her health problems. The healer prescribed her to do some YPV self-practice protocols, such as Rhythmic Breathing Exercises (RYB) and Forgiveness sadhana, explaining and emphasising on the importance of these practices to recover soon, while at the same time to receive YPV healings from the healer. Soon after the conversation, the patient started regular practice of Rhythmic Yogic Breathing (RYB) and Forgiveness Sadhana using guided tracks from free YPV Sadhana app. The healer continued checking on the patient's progress taking her feedback daily, while doing healing for her.

For treatment of right ovarian cysts, the healer gave healings for two weeks starting from 23 January to 6 February 2021, daily one session of 25 minutes.

For this purpose, the healer used protocols of

1. YPV Psychotherapy
2. YPV Level 5 healing for cyst

During this period of healing, the patient was observed to be experiencing very calm and relaxed state of being. A USG report taken on 8 February 2021 showed her right ovarian cysts disappeared completely.

Healing for Conception, Stable Pregnancy, and Safe Delivery:

From then onwards the patient was planning to conceive. On the patient's request, the healer started healing her again from 10 March 2021 to assist conception. The healer used the following protocols with crystal healing techniques from 10 March to 30 March 2021.

1. YPV Psychotherapy
2. YPV Level 5 healing for conceiving

As a result, the patient conceived successfully by the end of March 2021. Following this development, the healer continued giving healings for her for the next 8 months - from 31 March 2021 to 20 Oct 2021 as stated below.

31 March 2021 - 9 Oct 2021 (Healing using hands)

1. YPV Psychotherapy
2. YPV Healing using white color

10 Oct - 20 Oct 2021 (Healing using crystal)

1. YPV Psychotherapy
2. YPV Level 5 healing

In the month of May 2021, the patient had undergone a surgical procedure cervical stitch, on her uterus (at neck of cervix) through a medical intervention to avoid premature labour, because, according to medical assessment, her second miscarriage happened due to premature labour.

During this 3rd time pregnancy, she was on progesterone injections and medicines. She had chosen to have YPV healings as a complementary modality along with medications as she tried to sustain her conception in 3rd attempt. This time the patient made sure to have all things happen smoothly. During these eight months, many times, the healer healed her twice a day and during COVID thrice a day, with 25 minutes each session. The healer persisted on by reminding the patient to practice positive affirmations, RYB breathing, and forgiveness Sadhana.

Major challenges the patient experienced during the period of pregnancy were:

1. Incidence of Covid-19 during her 3rd month
2. Suffering from constipation, headaches, nausea
3. Negative thoughts and Anxiety
4. Fluctuating sugar levels

Accordingly, the healer addressed all these issues in the healing process with appropriate YPV protocols. The healer was closely monitoring the patient condition taking feedback twice-a-day. During October 2021, the healer healed her twice a day to manage fluctuating sugar levels.

RESULTS

The medical opinion of the patient's condition owing to all these factors, needed a C-section procedure for delivery, and accordingly on 9th October 2021 the patient delivered a healthy baby boy. Subsequent to the delivery, there were no reported health issues of the baby and the mother. During a follow up after 9 months in July 2022 it was confirmed that the mother and her baby both were in good health.

DISCUSSION

Ovarian cysts, pregnancy miscarriage and possibilities of fertility

Hemorrhagic ovarian cysts (HOCs) are frequently seen in reproductive age women, and are the most common type of ovarian cysts in India. Painful or large ovarian cysts may need to be removed with surgery [1]. Ovarian cysts are perhaps the most common issue among women trying to conceive. Not all cysts can be ignored as certain ovarian cysts can affect pregnancy and fertility [2].

Miscarriage is defined as spontaneous abortion without medical or mechanical means, terminating a pregnancy before the fetus is sufficiently developed to survive. The data on the prevalence of recurrent spontaneous miscarriage (RSM) in India are scarce. [3]

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Recurrent spontaneous miscarriage (RSM) is defined as three or more clinically recognized pregnancy losses prior to 20 weeks of gestation from the last menstrual period. It affects 1–2 % of women [3]. The occurrence of RSMs was found to be associated with clotting disorders, immunological factors, infections, and genetic disorders, and maternal age [3].

One or even two miscarriages are not, by themselves, indicative of future infertility. Nonetheless, they may leave patients concerned and questioning their ability to have a live birth. [4] Quite often, the reasons for miscarriage occurrences are not obvious, and many patients go on to have a successful third pregnancy. Even after two miscarriages, there's a 65% chance that third pregnancy will end in live birth. [4]

YOGA PRANA VIDYA SYSTEM

Yoga Prana Vidya system protocols have been known to have worked very well in the treatment of various diseases and illness conditions as complementary and also as an alternative medicine as observed in the published literature of over 55 research articles.

YPV system does not use any drugs nor touch. The healer acts as a channel to draw in and project Pranic energy to the patient's physical body parts as well as to the corresponding Chakrams of the energy body which distribute the given energy to the physical body, healing the patient holistically. As parts of an integrated system, the three categories of YPV protocols are: (1) Physical and Rhythmic breathing exercises for patient self-practice either by oneself or in groups, (2) Guided Meditations for practice of patients by oneself or in groups, and (3) energy healing, either self-healing, or by external trained healer. This way, a person's physical, mental and emotional domains are simultaneously healed enabling holistic treatment of co-existing conditions.

It is observed that this healer in this study applied YPV Level 5 healing, which has highly advanced techniques and requires high capability in healing, achieved through development by spiritual practices of Arhat Yoga Level 3 and above. One common path to achieve this level of competency according to the founder of YPV, is such that an aspirant would normally take a minimum 5 years of persistent effort, upgradation, actual application in healing and certification that this stage can be achieved. One other way to become Level 5 healer is: -

By those YPV healers who have achieved the healing proficiency of level 3 or 4, upgraded to Arhat yoga Level 3 or above in Spiritual practices and have done One Year Spiritual Intensive Program (OYSIP) at YPV Ashram, Sri Ramana Trust, and are upgraded during the one year as Level 5 healers in a Group.

Some examples of illness conditions successfully cured by YPV healing treatment protocols are: some difficult medical

cases, diabetes, arterial heart block, postherpetic neuralgia, exostosis of ear, vision improvements, high blood cholesterol and asthma, improved wellbeing and immunity, cases of first-aid and emergency, speedy recovery of COVID-19 patients, hypothyroidism, serious snakebite etc. [5-17]. There are also research studies conducted and papers published such as, a study on reduction in anxiety and depression of corporate employees [18], reduction in the criminal attitude of under-trial prisoners [19], improvement of IQ and social behaviour of mentally retarded children [20], effects of Planetary peace meditation conducted for over 100 high school students [21]. Some examples of successful cases of healing female reproductive system using YPV protocols are, An Endometriosis case [22], pregnancy and child birth [23] and a case of PCOS [24].

According to Medlineplus (National Library of Medicine, USA) [25], infertility means not being able to get pregnant after at least one year of trying (or 6 months if the woman is over age 35). If a woman keeps having miscarriages, it is also called infertility [25]. Cases such as this in this study have demonstrated the competency of YPV system in treating infertility successfully as complementary medicine.

CONCLUSIONS

The integrated and holistic system of Yoga Prana Vidya protocols have been established to successfully treat a variety of illness conditions as complementary and also as alternative system of medicine, as is evidenced by published literature. Further research using appropriate methodology and sample size is highly recommended. It may also be worthwhile to consider imparting training to all frontline healthcare workers including doctors and nurses, to gain a working knowledge of YPV to complement their treatment modalities for holistic healing at low cost without drugs that will be beneficial to patients.

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Role of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) System Protocols in Infertility Treatment: A Case Study Of A 29-Year-Old House Wife with History of Recurrent Spontaneous Miscarriages and Ovarian Cysts

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